

Kinetics of Oxidation of Atrolactic Acid by Ceric Salt

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The kinetics of oxidation of atrolactic acid (prepared from acetophenone) with ceric sulphate has been studied. The reaction was found to be of first order when the oxidant was used in excess and second order when the hydroxy acid was in excess. A sequence of reaction steps proposed explains satisfactorily this change in order of the reaction. The activation energy, frequency factor and entropy of activation were found to be 15.75 K.Cals/mole, 10^8 Sec.⁻¹ and -22.11 E.U. The rate of oxidation was retarded by H⁺ and also by the addition of a metal sulphate. The oxidation appears to proceed through an initial complex formation and subsequently through free radicals. The equilibrium constant of the complex and its rate of decomposition has been calculated.

Krishna and Tewari¹ and Sengupta *et al.*² have studied the oxidation of mandelic acid by ceric salt. The present investigation deals with the kinetics of oxidation of atrolactic acid by cerium sulphate with a view to study the effect of a methyl group on the rate and to study whether the presence of an α -hydrogen atom is necessary for the oxidation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ceric sulphate used was E. Merck's guaranteed reagent quality. Atrolactic acid was prepared from acetophenone. Ceric sulphate solution was prepared in 18N (1 : 1) sulphuric acid, diluted and standardised against ferrous ammonium sulphate solution using N-phenyl anthranilic acid as the indicator³.

Kinetic measurement : Equal volumes of Ce(SO₄)₂ (in aq. sulphuric acid) and atrolactic acid solutions, both of known concentration, were brought to the temperature of the thermostat and then mixed. The course of the reaction was then followed by withdrawing 5 ml. portions of the reaction mixture at definite intervals of time, chilling by ice to check the reaction and estimating the amount of the unchanged oxidant volumetrically by a standard Mohr's salt solution, using 2 drops of N-phenyl anthranilic acid as an indicator.

The products formed on oxidation were tested frequently and acetophenone was found as the reaction product. Stoichiometry⁴ was determined by mixing atrolactic acid with five to six times in molar concentrations of ceric sulphate solution and leaving the mixture at room temperature for several days. It was found that one mole of the acid requires two moles of ceric sulphate for oxidation to acetophenone.

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1. B. Krishna and K. C. Tewari, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 3097.
2. K. K. Sengupta, S. Aditya and B. N. Ghosh, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 825.
3. A. I. Vogel. "Quantitative Analysis", 1961, p. 319.
4. J. Shorter and C. N. Hinshelwood, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1959, 3277.

RESULTS

TABLE I

Dependence of rate on Ce(IV) at 30° 10^3 [Atrolactic acid] = 5.798(M); $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ = 2.0(M); Temp. = 30°

10^3 [Ce(SO ₄) ₂]	(M)	9.206	9.855	13.35	17.89
$k \times 10^4$ sec. ⁻¹		5.037	5.035	5.10	5.23

TABLE II

 10^3 [ALA] = 5.798 (M), $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ = 2.0 (M); Temp. = 30°

10^3 [Ce(SO ₄) ₂]	(M)	2.49	4.15	5.58
$k \times 10$ in mole ⁻¹ litre sec. ⁻¹		2.25	2.22	2.19

TABLE III

Effect of dilution on the rate of oxidation 10^3 [ALA] = 4.33 (M), $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ = 2.0 (M); Temp. = 30°

10^3 [Ce(SO ₄) ₂]	(M)	8.72	18.0	20.0	28.73	34.07
$k \times 10$ in mole ⁻¹ litre sec. ⁻¹		2.355	2.292	2.123	2.137	2.11

TABLE IV

Dependence of rate on atrolactic acid concentration 10^3 [Ce(SO₄)₂] = 6.56 (M), $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ = 2.0 (M), Temp. = 30°

10^3 [ALA]	(M)	2.32	3.48	4.64	5.79
$k \times 10^4$ in sec. ⁻¹		2.78	3.745	5.21	6.24
$k/[\text{ALA}]$ in mole ⁻¹ in sec. ⁻¹		0.1041	0.1076	0.1123	0.1076

TABLE V

Effect of temperature 10^3 [Ce(SO₄)₂] = 6.56 (M), 10^3 [ALA] = 4.64 (M), $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ = 2.0 (M)

Temp. °C.	25	30	35	E. in K.cals	log PZ	ΔS^\ddagger in E.U.
$k \times 10^4$ in sec. ⁻¹	3.157	5.208	7.980	15.75	7.99	-22.11

TABLE VI

Effect of Hydrogen ion concentration $10^3[\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2] = 7.105 (M)$, $10^3 [\text{ALA}] = 4.46 (M)$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 2.0 (M)$, Temp. = 30°

$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ in (M)	1.50	1.75	2.00	2.25	2.50	2.75
pH	-0.18	-0.24	-0.30	-0.36	-0.40	-0.45
$k \times 10^4$ in sec. ⁻¹	11.96	8.054	5.157	3.749	2.536	1.753

TABLE VII

Effect of added salt $10^3 [\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2] = 7.105 (M)$, $10^3 [\text{ALA}] = 4.64 (M)$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 2.0 (M)$, Temp = 30°

[Salt] in 0.1 (M)	Nil	Na_2SO_4	MgSO_4
$k \times 10^4$ in sec. ⁻¹	5.16	4.193	4.244

DISCUSSION

The oxidation is found to be of first order with respect to cerium (IV) and also to the hydroxy acid. The reaction is found to obey first order rate equation when the oxidant is in excess of the hydroxy acid (Table I). But when the hydroxy acid is in excess of the ceric salt, the reaction is found to be of second order (Table II). The same results have also been obtained by Krishna and Tewari¹ and Aditya *et al.*². The pseudo unimolecular rate constants depend upon the concentration of atrolactic acid (Table IV). It is observed that fairly constant values are obtained when these rate data are divided by the hydroxy acid concentration.

Influence of temperature : The Arrhenius equation is found to be valid in the temperature range studied. The slope of the straight line plot of $\log k$ versus $1/T$ gave the value of energy of activation to be 15.75 K.Calories. The frequency factor and the entropy of activation are found to be 10^8 Sec.^{-1} and -22.11 E.U. respectively.

The frequency factor for unimolecular decomposition process is usually observed to be more than $10^{10} \text{ Sec.}^{-1}$. The low value of the frequency factor and the negative entropy of activation value suggests a rigid transition state in the rate determining step.

Dependence on Acid : It is observed from Table IV that the values of rate constant decrease with increasing hydrogen ion concentration. It appears that the inhibitory effect observed on increasing the concentration of H_2SO_4 may be mainly due to bisulphate ion, by forming $\text{HCe}(\text{SO}_4)_3^-$.

The effect of addition of neutral salts *e.g.*, Na_2SO_4 and MgSO_4 (Vide Table VII) shows that they exhibit retarding effect and hence can corroborate the above observation. The $\log k$ values were then plotted against pH and H_0 values. A better fit of the data was obtained in the former case than in the latter case. This indicates that a molecule of water may be involved in the rate determining step of the reaction,

Effect of dilution of the reactants : The rate constants were determined at different concentrations of the reactants. The results (Table III) indicate that when the effect of hydrogen ion is taken into account, the rate constant is the same.

Mechanism : When atrolactic acid is oxidised by ceric sulphate acetophenone is obtained. When a large excess of ceric ion is present, two equivalents of ceric ions are consumed consequently :

can represent the stoichiometry of the equation.

Duke and Forist⁵ studied the oxidation of glycols by ceric ion and suggested that the first step in the reaction is the transfer of electron from the glycol to the metal in the higher oxidation state. This results in breaking of the C—C bond and formation of a free radical. Waters and Levesley⁶ also have proposed the formation of a free radical RĊHOH from a complex between the hydroxy acid and manganic pyrophosphate.

The reaction will obey the following equation, based on the theory of Duke⁷.

$$\frac{-d[\text{Ce(IV)}]}{dt} = \frac{k'K[\text{ALA}][\text{Ce(IV)}]}{1+K[\text{ALA}]}$$

where k' is the rate of decomposition of the complex and K is the equilibrium constant between the reactants and the complex.

$$\frac{-d[\text{Ce(IV)}]}{dt} = k[\text{Ce(IV)}]$$

where k is the observed rate constant, so by substituting this value and rearranging we get :

$$\frac{1}{k} = \frac{1}{k'K[\text{ALA}]} + \frac{1}{k'}$$

A straight line plot was obtained when $1/k$ was plotted against $1/[\text{ALA}]$ (Table IV) from the intercept and slope of which the rate of decomposition of the complex and the equilibrium constant values were found to be $33.3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ Sec.}^{-1}$ and $38.95 \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ litre}$ respectively.

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5. F. R. Duke and A. A. Foriest, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 2790.
6. W. A. Waters and P. Levesley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 217.
7. F. R. Duke, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 2885, 3054.